

Supporting Information for
Computational Study of the Adamantane
Cation: Simulations of Spectroscopy,
Fragmentation Dynamics, and Internal
Conversion

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Table S1 Bond distances $r(\text{C-H})$ and $R(\text{C-C})$ (in nm) and angles (in degrees) of neutral and cationic adamantane.

Neutral	OM2	OM3	AM1	PM3	PM7	B3LYP/ 6-31G*	
r_1	0.113	0.114	0.112	0.111	0.111	0.110	
r_2	0.112	0.112	0.112	0.111	0.110	0.110	
r_3	0.113	0.114	0.112	0.111	0.111	0.110	
r_4	0.112	0.112	0.112	0.111	0.110	0.110	
r_5	0.112	0.112	0.112	0.111	0.110	0.110	
R_1	0.153	0.154	0.153	0.153	0.154	0.154	
R_2	0.153	0.154	0.153	0.153	0.154	0.154	
R_3	0.153	0.154	0.153	0.153	0.154	0.154	
α_1	109.4	109.5	109.5	109.5	109.5	109.6	
α_2	109.4	109.4	109.3	109.4	109.4	109.3	
α_3	109.4	109.5	109.6	109.6	109.6	109.7	
α_4	109.7	109.6	109.6	109.5	109.4	109.3	
α_5	109.3	109.4	109.6	109.6	109.6	109.7	
Cation	OM2	OM3	AM1	PM3	PM7	UB3LYP/ 6-31G*	ROOM3/ CISD(9x10)
r_1	0.116	0.116	0.117	0.116	0.119	0.113	0.116
r_2	0.111	0.111	0.112	0.111	0.111	0.109	0.111
r_3	0.112	0.113	0.112	0.112	0.112	0.110	0.113
r_4	0.111	0.112	0.112	0.111	0.111	0.110	0.112
r_5	0.111	0.112	0.113	0.111	0.112	0.110	0.112
R_1	0.151	0.151	0.151	0.151	0.151	0.152	0.151
R_2	0.157	0.158	0.157	0.158	0.160	0.161	0.158
R_3	0.152	0.153	0.151	0.152	0.152	0.153	0.152
α_1	105.7	105.5	106.2	105.4	105.2	105.8	105.6
α_2	112.9	113.1	112.6	113.2	113.4	112.9	113.1
α_3	105.3	105.1	105.9	105.0	105.0	105.6	105.1
α_4	108.3	108.0	108.0	107.9	107.8	107.2	107.8
α_5	110.3	110.6	110.6	110.7	110.7	111.1	110.6

Table S2 Dominant molecular orbital pairs (each including an initial and a final molecular orbital) for transitions from D_0 to D_1 – D_4 , calculated with TD-UB3LYP/6-31G* (the “B3LYP” column) and ROOM3/CISD(9×10) (the “MNDO” column), at the UB3LYP/6-31G* optimized geometry.

Adamantane : B3LYP Geometry						
State	B3LYP		MNDO			
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final		
D_1	<p>MO: MO(1) MO(2) MO(3) Energy = 0.0000 Occupancy = 2</p> <p>28</p>					
D_2	<p>MO: MO(1) MO(2) MO(3) Energy = 0.0000 Occupancy = 2</p> <p>28</p>					
D_3	<p>MO: MO(1) MO(2) MO(3) Energy = 0.0000 Occupancy = 2</p> <p>28</p>					
D_4	<p>MO: MO(1) MO(2) MO(3) Energy = 0.0000 Occupancy = 2</p> <p>28</p>					

Table S3 Dominant molecular orbital pairs (each including an initial and a final molecular orbital) for transitions from D_0 to D_5 – D_8 , calculated with TD-UB3LYP/6-31G* (the “B3LYP” column) and ROOM3/CISD(9×10) (the “MNDO” column), at the UB3LYP/6-31G* optimized geometry.

Adamantane : B3LYP Geometry				
State	B3LYP		MNDO	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
D_5	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.022 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 28			
D_6	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.033 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 28			
D_7	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.033 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 28			
D_8	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.033 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 28			

Table S4 Dominant molecular orbital pairs (each including an initial and a final molecular orbital) for transitions from D_0 to D_9 and D_{10} , calculated with TD-UB3LYP/6-31G* (the “B3LYP” column) and ROOM3/CISD(9×10) (the “MNDO” column), at the UB3LYP/6-31G* optimized geometry.

Adamantane : B3LYP Geometry				
State	B3LYP		MNDO	
	Initial	Final	Initial	Final
D_9	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.033 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 29			
D_{10}	 <small>mndofinal MO#11 MO 20/98 alpha Energy = 0.033 Symmetry = 4 Occupancy = 2</small> 30			

Table S5 Excited states of the cation at the geometry of the neutral — TD-DFT@[DFT neutral (S_0) minimum], DFT = (U)B3LYP/6-31G*.

Transition	E (eV)	f
$D_0 \rightarrow D_1$	0.0873	0.0000
$D_0 \rightarrow D_2$	0.0873	0.0000
$D_0 \rightarrow D_3$	1.2516	0.0000
$D_0 \rightarrow D_4$	1.3343	0.0121
$D_0 \rightarrow D_5$	1.3343	0.0121
$D_0 \rightarrow D_6$	1.3493	0.0000
$D_0 \rightarrow D_7$	1.4262	0.0164
$D_0 \rightarrow D_8$	3.0934	0.0000
$D_0 \rightarrow D_9$	3.1493	0.0463
$D_0 \rightarrow D_{10}$	3.1493	0.0463

Fig. S1 Relative abundance for scenario (a) when using Wigner initial conditions (with rescaled velocities) and photon energy $E_{h\nu} = 3$ eV. The excess energy is ~ 6.1 eV. Propagation time is 10 ps. 7 % of trajectories showed rearrangement of the adamantane cage.

Fig. S2 Population of 5 states for the simulations starting from the D_1 and D_2 states.

Fig. S3 Population of 5 states for simulations starting from the D_3 and D_4 states.

Fig. S4 Population of 10 states for the simulations starting from the energy window between 2.3 eV to 2.9 eV.

Fig. S5 Population of 10 states for simulations starting from the D_8 state.